

Deep learning based holographic microscope image focusing and object classification

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Thesis Proposal Form

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Thesis

Title: Deep learning based holographic microscope image focusing and object classification

Summary of the thesis:

Holographic microscope images need post processing and image understanding to draw proper conclusions in automatic processes. The major tasks are object detection, object segmentation, focusing, and classification. The goal of this thesis work is to develop and evaluate deep learning based focusing and classification methods for objects captured in biological samples.

Detailed task description:

- Learn the operational principles of the digital holographic microscope
- Study the scientific literature of the focusing and image classification problem for objects captured by digital holographic microscope
- Study the available annotated databases, and make some additional annotations where needed
- Define the focusing and classification strategy and the corresponding network
- Implement and train the network
- Evaluate the results
- Write the thesis work

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1 Abstract

During the past decade the huge advancements in terms of computational power and resources implied the exponential development of the different hardware demanding machine learning techniques. One of the most popular area in this field are the different, biologically inspired microscopic image processing methods. Here two important steps are finding the proper focus plane for a sharp image and additionally segmenting or detecting the most important areas (objects) on the images. This is the situation also with the Digital holographic microscopy (DHM), which is a proper technique for the imaging of three dimensional objects, because — compared to conventional microscopes — it has better depth-of-field through allowing the reconstruction of a volume with multiple in-focus planes.

In this thesis work I propose deep learning based solutions to firstly find the focus planes of the objects on the DHM recordings, and then segment their locations with their types as well. For these, I implemented different kinds of convolutional neural networks using the Python programming language and the PyTorch framework.

Regarding the focus distance estimation, after the architecture of the network has been designed and implemented, 3 different setup was inspected for finding an optimal solution: The target distances (direction - positive and negative distances included, absolute - absolute value of the distances), the activation function in the last layer (hyperbolic tangent or sigmoid) and the inclusion or exclusion of the phase images into the input of the net.

Concerning the image segmentation, the task here was more complex. Here the available labelled images for the ground truth were not accurate enough, thus I firstly developed an image processing tool, which had two main functionalities: image augmentation through transformations and semi-automatic image labelling. Then, as the next step a simple object segmentor net (SOSN) was implemented, which was developed to simply segment the objects without classifying them. Following that, using the results of the SOSN, it was adapted to also segment the types of the objects with different colors, this was the simple semantic segmentor net (SSSN). And as the last steps, I implemented two variations of the state-of-the-art U-Net architectures, for being able to better evaluate the results of the SSSN and also gain ideas based on the differences for its further development.

2 Introduction

During the last few years exponential developments in terms of computational power and resources made it possible to use different kind of machine learning techniques for image processing purposes. This also enhanced the field of the biologically inspired microscopic image processing, where the two main problems are the proper image focusing and the object detection/segmentation. This is also the case in some non-conventional modalities like the Digital holographic microscopy, which we used for acquiring our images.

2.1 Digital holographic microscopy

Digital holographic microscopy (DHM) is a single-shot and label-free microscopic modality, which is well applicable for the imaging of 3 dimensional objects [4]. While the conventional optical microscopes record the projected image of the object using incoherent light, digital holographic microscopes use the interference of the coherent waves scattered from the object and a reference wave to create the hologram. Then, as a post processing step, using the previously acquired hologram and reconstruction algorithms, a computer creates a viewable image from the object.

Due to this imaging technique, DHM is much less sensitive to the depth-of-field compared to conventional microscopes, which allows us to do the reconstruction of a volume at different in-focus planes. Also, thanks to these properties, an other big advantage of this imaging technique is, that refocusing can be done numerically by using a single hologram, so there is no need to do any additional mechanical scanning. Even with these advantages, we still face with the problem, that an object is in focus only at a few depths, because a single reconstruction layer still has a shallow depth-of-field. For solving this problem, many different methods have been worked out. There are solutions, which try to fix this issue with amplitude analysis[7], self-entropy[9], power spectra[15] and with other kind of techniques[1]. These are so called wavelength methods where they reconstruct a stack of images and then this procedure will be applied to each of the holograms.

Despite having these advantages and already existing solutions, DHM systems are not as commonly used as conventional microscopes due to some well known problems like the "missing phase problem" and coherence related artifacts (i.e. speckle noise and multiple reflection interference). Nowadays however, as we are gaining more and more computational power and the field of deep learning is also exponentially develop-

ing, these challenges can be eliminated with high efficiency while maintaining all the previously mentioned advantageous properties of coherent imaging. There are already existing solutions using deep learning techniques for phase recovery[24][28][33][10], phase unwrapping[5][29], super resolution[19] and label-free sensing[34][11][32], which are all using optimized deep convolutional neural networks for achieving their purposes.

2.2 Convolutional neural networks

Convolutional neural networks are one form of deep learning techniques, and have been successfully used for different image processing purposes[16][14]. The term "convolution" refers to the mathematical operation it is based on and it means that it has at least one layer, which performs convolution.

In connection with the convolutional neural networks, convolution is a linear operation that performs multiplication between the set of weights and the input data just like the conventional neural networks do. The difference between them is, that this kind of network was designed for 2 or more dimensional input data and its set of weights are also organized into 2 or more dimensional grids, called filters or kernels. The filter or kernel size is much smaller than the input data, it usually has a size from 3x3 to 5x5. The multiplication is applied using dot product among the filter and the filter-sized patch of the input data, which means that element-wise multiplication will be performed and then they will be summed up which results in a single value. After this value has been calculated, the filter moves further on the input data, so it examines a new filter-sized patch of the input. The magnitude of the steps or movements are called stride and it is usually among 1-3 units resulting overlaps between the different patches.

This structured scanning of the same kernel across the input image is a very powerful tool, since a specific kernel can be used and adapted to scan for a certain feature across the whole image. As the scanning is ongoing, one single value is generated for each patch-filter pairs, resulting a 2 dimensional output array called feature map. Once a feature map is created, each value of it can be passed further to some nonlinear terms (i.e. ReLu), whose output will be the input of the subsequent layer. The above mentioned flow of scanning can be seen on the following figure as well:

Figure 1: *The scanning procedure of the kernels in convolutional neural networks*

After the data has passed through all the layers of the network, the output of the last layer is given to a user-defined cost or loss function (i.e. mean squared error)[26], which calculates an error based on some ground truth data. The aim of the whole training is to adjust the weights of the filters in such a way, that they produce minimal errors.

Just like other kinds of neural networks, convolutional neural networks were also inspired by biological observations, in this case by the connectivity patterns and the firing properties of the neurons in the animal visual cortex [8]. Here the individual neurons strictly belong to one restricted region of the visual field, and are sensitive only for such stimuli, which are coming from this region, also called as the receptive field. Besides, they are specialized for different shapes of the objects (i.e vertical or horizontal edges) and thus they are fired only when these features are present on their receptive field. Between the receptive fields there are overlappings, so the functioning is very similar to the convolutional layers.

2.3 Image segmentation and object detection

Similarly to other image processing purposes, convolutional neural networks are one of the most suitable deep learning techniques also for the image segmentation tasks. Image segmentation means that we divide the input image into multiple different segments, where each pixel of the image will be associated with an object label, a class label or

both. It is actually a superset of the image classification problem, where the network is not just classifying the image based on the objects on it, but it also provides information related to the location of the different objects. There are three main types of image segmentation: The first one is called semantic segmentation, where every object, which belong to the same type are labelled with the same number. The second type is called instance segmentation, where each distinct object is labelled with a unique number. And the name of the third type is panoptic segmentation, which can be thought of as the combination of the semantic and instance segmentation. This means, that we classify each pixel of the image with a class label and in the same time they also get an object label, which associates them with given object instance on the image. This segmentation type is especially used for example in the self driving cars, where not just the object types are important, but it's also crucial to separate the distinct objects belonging to the same class.

The above mentioned differences between the segmentation types can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 2: *The different segmentation types. Top left section: original image; Bottom left: semantic segmentation of the image; Bottom right: instance segmentation; Top right: panoptic segmentation. On the panoptically segmented image it can be seen, that this type is the combination of the semantic and instance segmentation, the colors are merged.[6]*

In the field of image segmentation, several AI based methods and architectures have been developed, these are mainly based on convolutional neural networks. In the following sections the most famous and widely used ones will be described in more detail.

2.3.1 Fully convolutional neural networks

Fully convolutional neural networks (FCN) were firstly proposed by Long *et al.*[21] and it was originally developed for semantic image segmentation. The network and its variations have been widely used to a range of image segmentation problems, including instance-aware semantic segmentation[17], brain tumor segmentation[31], iris segmentation[18] and skin lesion segmentation[35].

From the architectural point of view, FCN contains only convolutional layers, where the authors modified already existing CNN architectures, like the AlexNet[14] and VGG16[27]. Here they replaced all the fully connected layers with convolutional layers, which enabled them to handle non fixed-sized input images and produce a segmentation map with the same size. On the following figure the architecture of this network can be seen:

Figure 3: *The architecture of the fully convolutional neural network. Here the number and the width next to the different layers show the number of the feature maps.[21]*

As it is visible on the figure above, after a stack of fully convolutional, so called contracting path, the feature maps of the last layers are suddenly up-sampled and moreover, they are fused with the feature maps of the earlier, higher resolution layers through "skipped connections". This allows the network to merge the semantic information (from the deep, low resolution layers) with appearance information (from the first few high resolution layers).

Although this architecture had a huge success, and it achieved state-of-the-art segmentation performance, it certainly has some limitations, which restricts the usability of it. For example it has runtime related problems, which means that it is not fast enough for the real-time prediction. Besides, it also has limitations regarding the way it handles

the global context information. To overcome these problems a lot of solution proposals have been made.

For instance, there is a model called ParseNet[20], where the authors try to handle the issue related to global context information processing. In their paper they enhance this performance by using average feature in a layer, which means that the feature map of the layer is pooled over the entire image, which at the end results in a context vector. Then this context vector will be normalized and goes through a procedure called unpooling, which produces again a feature map with the same dimensions as the original maps. And lastly, the generated feature map will be concatenated with the original ones. So actually in short, the ParseNet can be described as a FCN, where the convolutional layers are replaced by this enhanced layer module. The following figure shows the above mentioned working principles of the improved module:

Figure 4: *The basic module of the ParseNet. It shows how the feature map of a layer is processed separately in two ways and then the results are merged together.[20]*

2.3.2 Encoder and decoder based models

Beside the FCN, another very popular family of CNN used for image segmentation purposes is the encoder and decoder architecture. The principle of operation of these architectures is based on convolutional layers and on two, nearly symmetrical paths.

The first one is called as the encoder path — which is also called as the contracting path — that consists of a stack of traditional convolutional and pooling layers. This layers work as conventional convolutional layers, so they encode the input image into a bunch of feature map representations in multiple different levels. This process results, that the output of each layer has lower and lower resolutions (especially after the pooling layers), however the number of channels/feature maps increases for being able to store image context informations.

The second path of the network is called as the decoder path and it consists of symmetric expanding layers. The goal of this section is to project the condensed, lower resolution

feature maps learnt by the encoder into the pixel space and through multiple steps create higher and higher resolution feature maps, which at the end have nearly the same resolution as our input image had. The operation, which creates these higher resolution outputs is called transposed convolution or deconvolution. A typical architecture of this family can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 5: *The typical encoder and decoder based network. On the left side the contracting pathway is visible, which creates the dense feature maps. On the right side the decoder path can be seen, which projects the dense feature maps into the higher resolution pixel space.*[23]

In the field of the encoder and decoder architectures there are special ones, which were originally developed for biomedical image segmentation purposes. Two very good examples are the V-Net[22] and the U-Net[25].

The U-Net is a type of convolutional neural network architecture, which was developed at the Computer Science Department of the University of Freiburg in 2015[25]. As is was mentioned above, originally it was created for biomedical purposes, for segmenting biological microscope images, however after a while it turned out that they can be efficiently used for other type of segmentation tasks as well. The training strategy of this network was focused on to also work efficiently with a low number of annotated/labelled data. Like the other encoder and decoder architectures, the U-Net also has a contracting pathway for capturing context information. The layers of this pathway consists of fully convolutional units, which are combined with max pooling layers. The kernel sizes for these layers are 3x3 and 2x2, respectively.

The up-sampling part of the network — like the other encoder and decoder family networks — contains deconvolving layers, which reduce the number of feature maps and projects them into the width and height dimensions. Additionally to the outputs of the deconvolving layers, the feature maps of the same level in the contracting pathway are copied over and concatenated with the deconvolved outputs, which helps to avoid the loss of pattern information. At the end, in the last layer, a convolution with a kernel

size of 1×1 scans the feature maps and generates an already segmented output, where the pixels are already labelled with different categories.

The above mentioned procedures and the architecture of the U-Net can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 6: *The architecture of the U-Net. Here the blue boxes represent the stacks of the feature maps and the white boxes represent the copied maps coming from the contracting pathway. The arrows are showing different operations, which are labelled at the right bottom corner.*[25]

As the U-Net appeared it immediately had a huge success. For example, it won the ISBI cell tracking challenge in 2015 and was trained only by 30 transmitted light microscopy images. Due to these successes, various extensions have been developed in the past few years to adapt the U-Net to different kind of segmentation purposes. Among these there were modifications which adapted it for 3D images[3], Zhou *et al.* modified it to a nested U-Net architecture[37], and also there were examples, where the authors used it for road segmentation tasks[36].

Beside the U-Net, another famous and important network belonging to this architecture family is the so called V-Net. It is also an FCN based model like the U-Net and originally it was developed for 3D medical image segmentation[22]. At this model, an important modification was that the authors introduced a new loss function, which is based on the Dice coefficient. This allowed the network to handle those cases appropriately, where the imbalance between the foreground and background voxels was too high. The

original network was trained exclusively on MRI prostate volumes, however due to the successes here again there were extensions which enabled the usage of it for other kind of recordings. For instance a variant of it, the Progressive Dense V-Net (PDV-Net) was developed for fast and automatic segmentation of pulmonary lobes based on chest CT recordings[12], and another variant was the 3D-CNN encoder for lesion segmentation[2].

The high success rate and the efficiency of these encoder and decoder based networks may be traced back to the similarity between the architecture of them and the converging and diverging pathway in the vertebrate visual processing system. For example in case of the human the number of the photoreceptor cells (rods and cones) in the first layer of the visual processing pathway is estimated to be around 126 million. The information, which is gathered by these photoreceptors is passed on to the next processing layers of the retina, where the number of cells is getting fewer and fewer after each cell layer. At the last layer, where the so called ganglion cells are located, the number is reduced to 1.2 million, which means that the ratio between the photoreceptor and ganglion cells is 100:1. This form of information convergence is very similar to the contracting pathway of these architectures, where the resolution of the input image is reduced significantly till the end of the encoder path.

On the other hand, the second part of the visual processing pathway can be characterized with divergence, where the number of processing neurons is increased from layer to layer. The 1.2 million axons of the ganglion cells are firstly projected to the optic chiasma, where the lateral fibers continue their way on the same side, however the medial fibers are crossing the borders of the two cerebral hemispheres and continue their way on the other side. Then, these fibers are ending on an important relay and information processing station called the Lateral geniculate nucleus in the thalamus. This station has already a much higher number of cells, the number of axons/fibers which are exiting from this section is estimated to be approximately 5 million. At the last stations, at the primary, secondary and higher visual cortex areas, the number of neurons, which are associated with visual information processing is higher than 500 million. The following figure shows these converging and diverging pathways of the human visual processing system:

Figure 7: *The converging and diverging pathways of the human visual processing system. On the top, the number of the processing cells and axons is visible, which are associated with the different processing layers. On the bottom, the name of the different structures and the size of them can be seen.[13]*

2.3.3 Related works

Deep learning techniques for solving object segmentation in DHM images are not so common as segmenting objects in normal light microscope images, however there are some researches, where the authors tried to solve this problems. In one of them, Valadares *et al.* used different kind of machine learning techniques and evaluated the performance of each[30]. The first convolutional neural network they proposed is a so called auto-encoder.

Auto-encoder neural network is a type of unsupervised deep learning technique, which in terms of the architecture is based on the encoder and decoder models. Compared to the previously mentioned models the biggest difference is, that we do not have here a labelled ground truth image, instead the aim is to reconstruct the input image. During the training the network learns how to encode the most relevant features, which are present on the input picture and at the end of the decoder pathway we get back an approximate of the original input in a denoised manner.

The auto-encoder network in the proposal of Valadares *et al.* had three encoder and four decoder blocks. An encoder block contained four basic layers. The first one was a convolutional layer, which was followed by a batch normalization layer. The output of the batch normalization was mapped by the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation

function, which gives its output to the fourth max pooling layer.

In the first block the convolutional layer contained 16 kernels with a size of 7x7, the second block’s convolutional layer had 32 kernels with 5x5 dimensions and the third consisted of 64 kernels with dimensions of 3x3.

Similarly to the encoder pathway, the blocks of the decoder part also contained four layers, these were an upsampling layer at the beginning which was followed by a transposed convolutional layer. Then again batch normalization was used on the output of the deconvolutional layer, and at the end the normed output is mapped by the ReLU activation function.

The parameters used for the deconvolutional layers in the decoder are symmetrical with those ones which were used for the convolutional layers in the encoder. This means, that for the first decoder block the deconvolutional layer had 64 kernels with 3x3 dimensions, the second one had 32 filters with a size of 5x5, and the third one consisted of 16 kernels with 7x7 dimension sizes. The very last block in the decoder contained only a convolutional layer with a sigmoid activation function, which generates a 2D segmentation map of the image. Considering other parameters, the network used a stride of 1x1 in each convolutional and deconvolutional layers of the encoder and decoder and also the padding was set to a value of 1x1[30]. The basic architectural overview of the above mentioned auto-encoder network can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 8: *The basic architecture of the auto-encoder network, which was used in the paper of Valadares et al. As it can be seen, the encoder and decoder pathways are symmetrical except the last block of the decoder.[30]*

The other type of network which was used by Valadares *et al.* was the U-Net. For that the authors tested different variations/configurations of the U-Net architecture. Firstly they used a variation, where the U-Net had pre-trained weights on the 2012 ILSVRC ImageNet dataset and during the further trainings these weights were not locked, they

were free for the update. Since the pre-training of this network was executed on RGB images (three input channels), an additional convolutional layer had to be added to the very beginning of the net for mapping the two channel input of the DHM images to the three input channels of the network.

The second type of configuration was very similar to the first one, it was also pre-trained on the previously mentioned dataset. The difference between the two was, that in the second type the encoder weights were frozen, which means that only the decoder weights were updated during the training.

Then, in the third version of the network a slight modification was applied during the training compared to the second one. In this configuration the network was trained the same way as the previous one, however the weights of the encoder were only frozen at the beginning of the training, for the remaining parts they were free for the update.

And the last version of the network was different in terms of the weights compared to the previous ones. In this setup they used the same U-Net architecture, however the weights were not pre-trained at all. This also meant that the convolutional layer at the very beginning, which was applied for mapping the two channel DHM image input into three channels was no longer necessary.

For the training and the validation of the networks the authors used 1000 samples of DHM images from which 700 images were used for the training and the remaining 300 were used for the testing and validation purposes. Each of the network types were trained for 50 epochs with a batch size of 10 and Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 was used for achieving better learning performance.

For the loss function the authors used binary cross-entropy and during the evaluation the errors for the background and object pixels were assessed separately. This means that the proportion of background pixels which were misclassified as object pixels and the proportion of those object pixels which were incorrectly classified as background pixels were calculated and evaluated separately. Apart from these the time required for generating the segmented output was also measured.

The overall result was, that among the U-Nets the best performance was achieved with the U-Net of the first configuration (pre-trained weights and all of them were free for the update during the whole training time). With this setting they achieved an object error rate of 4.75%, a background error rate of 0.054% and the time required for the output generation was in average 0.127 seconds[30]. Comparing this to the results of the auto-

encoder, the error rates here were 10.49% and 0.132% for the object and background, respectively, and the required time for the segmented image generation was 0.085 seconds. So overall, the first type of the U-Net achieved a better segmenting accuracy than the auto-encoder, however it required a bit more time for generating the output due to the depth of its architecture. The differences between the two outputs can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 9: *The output of the U-Net and the auto-encoder models for a random image selected from the validation set. As it can be seen, the output of the U-Net is more clear and accurate compared to the auto-encoder output, which contains some noise artefacts.*[30]

3 Description of the used solutions and results

In the last sections we have seen deep learning models, which are widely used in different kind of segmentation problems and also some methods have been mentioned at the beginning, which are used for the reconstruction of the focus images from the DHM recordings.

These methods were important in the Introduction, since my thesis work also contains these two main topics. During my work, my first task was to create an AI, neural network based model for estimating the focus distance of the different DHM recordings and after that develop again another model, which aims to detect/segment and classify the objects which are present on these recordings. For the implementation I used the python programming language and the PyTorch framework, which is a very powerful library for machine learning purposes.

So, in the following sections firstly those methods will be described, which were used for the focus distance estimation, and then we are going to see those techniques as well, which were used for the object segmentation and classification.

3.1 Focus distance estimation

For estimating the focus distance of the DHM recordings, I tried out different kind of techniques, which were all based on a convolutional neural network architecture. This architecture was slightly modified and adapted for the different techniques, however the key properties (i.e. the number of used layers, number of feature map outputs of the layers) remained the same. The main properties of this architecture is summarised in the following table:

Layer	Layer type	In channels	Out channels	Kernel size	Stride	Padding
1	Conv. + ReLu	1-2	32	5	2	0
2	Conv. + ReLu	32	64	5	2	0
3	Conv. + ReLu	64	128	5	2	0
4	Conv. + ReLu	128	256	5	2	0
5	Avg. Pooling	256	256	-	-	-
6	Conv. + Sig/Tanh	256	1	1	1	0

Table 1: *The architecture of the used convolutional neural network. During my work, I applied some changes to that (experiments with tanh and sigmoid activation functions at the last layer), but the main concepts like the number of layers did not change.*

As it can be seen above, the used architecture is built up from 6 layers. From this 3 different layer types can be distinguished.

The first type can be seen at the first 4 layer levels. Here convolutional layers were used and at the end of the convolution the results were passed to ReLu (Rectified Linear Unit, $f(x) = \max(0, x)$) activation function. Here, an additional feature also can be observed, namely that each layer has double so many out channels (or kernels/convolutional features) as the previous one.

The next type belongs only to the 5. layer, this layer performs an average pooling. This average pooling means, that the layer receives 256 2x2 sized input channels per picture and conducts an average calculation on each channel, resulting in 256 1x1 sized channels per image.

And the last layer type is layer 6. Here, just like in the case of the first 4 layers, the basic operation is the convolution, however the activation function differs from the previous convolutional layers. Here in the latest state, I used the sigmoid activation function, which maps the output values of the convolution between $[0, 1]$, but during my work I also had experiments with the hyperbolic tangent function whose codomain is $[-1, 1]$ (later will be described in details). Another difference is in this layer, that instead of increasing the output channel number compared to the number of input channels, it reduces it from 256 to 1 and "summarizes" the features which were coming from the pooling layer into a single number, which will be passed to the used activation function. So, as it can be seen, after the last layer, the output will be one single value, which should correspond to the distance of the actual image from the focus point.

3.1.1 Training and test data

For the training and test data, we had 2 types of sources, 2 databases. At the beginning we used the first database, it contained approximately 4000 pictures without phase informations. The second one was exported later, but it contained already more then 60000 pictures and phase informations were also included in them. The pictures had a resolution of 128x128 pixels and only contained one channel, so they were grayscaled (that's why the first convolutional layer had only 1 channel instead of 3 like in the case of an RGB image). During the reading and the preprocessing of the images, the resolution was converted to 64x64 pixels for speeding up the velocity of the learning/training.

For the testing purposes, a group of images were separated from the training data, so when I tested the neural network, these images were not seen before. The number of test samples were about 5-10% of the training sample number.

3.1.2 Targets

The images, which were used for the training were organized into groups. A group contained a sequence of pictures taken from the same object from different distances. In general a group contained 19 pictures, and usually the middle one, so the 10th picture was the one, which was in focus. The steps between the pictures were about 100 micrometers in the magnified space (around 5 micrometers in the original space), so the first and the 19th pictures were approximately in -1mm and +1mm distances from the focus. When these images were given to the network as a training or test sample, this distance value and also the focus distance for the given group were contained by the picture's filename. Using these information the difference between the actual and the focus distance could be calculated and then normalized by a number, in this case by 1000. So for instance, if we have a picture whose actual distance is 5560 micrometers and the focus distance for that group is 5060 micrometers, then the difference is +500 micrometers, which afterwards will be normalized to 0.5. This number then was given to the network as the target number for that specific image.

However regarding the targets, there were limitations as well, which required some image preprocessing mechanism from the network. The main issue with the images was, that there were groups, where the image in the focus was not the middle one (10th picture), so the targets in the group did not always range from -1.0 to +1.0, they could range for instance from -0.8 til +1.2.

This range shift issue is a serious problem, because targets below -1.0 and above 1.0 cannot be used due to the codomain limits of the hyperbolic tangent and sigmoid activation function (if we take the absolute value of the distances). A solution could be for this issue, that we normalize the targets with a higher number, with i.e 10000, meaning that the range of the learnable distances would be extended to a [-10mm, +10mm] range from the focus.

This however has the problem that most of this range would not be used by the network (the maximum distance among the pictures were about 1.5mm) and apart from that it would be much harder for the network to distinguish the distances, because the difference of the target distances between two neighbouring images would also decrease by a factor of 10 (for instance an image with 400 micrometer distance would have a target of 0.04 and the neighbouring one with 500 micrometer distance would have a target of 0.05).

So due to this limitation of a higher normalization number I rather remained at the

original normalization factor of 1000 and implemented a function, which filters out all the pictures, whose target is below -1.0 or above 1.0.

Apart from the overshooting of the activation functions codomain, this range shift also caused an other issue. This issue was that in such a "shifted" group there are targets, which does not have a picture. Using the example which was mentioned above (from -0.8 til +1.2 shift), here the targets -0.9 and -1.0 does not have a picture. If we project this group example to the whole training set, we can say that the pictures are not equally distributed among the different targets, which is a problem regarding the neural network training. For example if we have 70 pictures for target 0.6, but only 55 pictures for target 0.9, than this can cause an incorrect gradient optimization during the backpropagation, which will end up in the wrong estimations for pictures which belong to target 0.9.

Due to this issue, another filtering technique also had to be implemented. So after the filtering step mentioned above, the remaining pictures are shuffled up and then a given number of pictures are selected for each target. This number of training samples per target was set by a parameter, which is usually equal to the number of pictures of that target, which have the smallest amount of images. After that, the list of the chosen pictures are returned, which will be the final version of the training samples that will be given to the network. Using this double filtering technique for the proper learning, approximately half of the images of the whole dataset can be given to the network at once.

3.1.3 Focus distance prediction with direction

The first training was conducted using hyperbolic tangent activation function in the last layer and pictures from the first database. Due to the filtering reasons mentioned above, from the 4000 pictures maximum only 2500 pictures could be included into this training. The hyperbolic tangent function has a codomain of $[-1, 1]$ and it was used because at the beginning we also wanted to distinguish the positive and negative distances from the focus point. So here considering the architecture I used one input channel at the first layer for the grayscale images (it did not contain phase informations) and hyperbolic tangent activation function at the last layer. The training images were given to the network in batches, usually I chose a batch size to be equal with the number of targets, so in this case a size of 21. For the optimization of the training and learning speed,

Adam optimizer was used. At the first run the learning rate was set to the default 0.001 value, however it turned out that this value is too high, so I set it to 0.0001. Using these parameters I got the following learning curves:

Figure 10: *The learning curves using hyperbolic tangent activation function and a learning rate of 0.0001. The x axis shows the batch index and the y axis shows the L1 loss.*

Here 116 pictures were used for each target, so overall 2436 pictures were included into the training. The left picture is the first run, after that the weights were saved and the second run (right picture) used already these optimized weights. On the left picture a sudden cutdown is visible that is due to an automatic checking system in the code, which stops the learning after the error goes below a given threshold for the last 10 batches.

As it can be seen on *Figure 10*, the network is learning very well, however using these positive and negative distances I faced with an issue, which comes up quite frequently when someone teaches a neural network for focusing. This issue was, that the network could estimate the absolute distance of the focus quite well for the test images (the average error was about 0.14 if we only take the absolute value), but often it swapped the sign of it. So to show an example, for a picture whose target was 0.5 it could estimate around -0.59. Because of this issue, the average loss could not go below 0.3, which is approximately a 70% accuracy. A comparison between two pictures of the same group, which have the same distance in absolute value can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 11: 3 images from the same group. The middle one is in focus, the left one has a target of -0.8 and the right one's target is $+0.8$. As it can be seen there is no big difference between the 2 pictures, however the target difference is 1.6 , which can lead to high $L1$ loss values.

3.1.4 Absolute focus distance prediction

After I faced with the issue mentioned above, I tried out another approach, namely using sigmoid as the activation function in the last layer, so actually giving the absolute value of the given distance to the network as the target (the targets ranged now from 0.0 to 1.0). I tried out 2 different techniques: The first one was to train the network with single images and the second one was to include phase informations as well. Here we had already the second database exported, so approximately 60000 pictures were available, but after the appliance of the filters this was reduced to 37000 pictures (3360 image per target).

3.1.4.1 Training with single images

For the single image training the architecture did not change too much compared to the previous training, only the activation function was replaced to sigmoid in the last layer, the number of input channels in the first layer remained one. However I increased a bit the learning rate to 0.0003 , because we had here more training samples. The learning curve and the results on the test set I got with this technique can be seen on *Figure 12*:

Figure 12: *The learning curve and the output of the test for the training with sigmoid activation function using single images.*

On the right picture, the top figure shows the well assessed test sample in percentage. This means that after rounding the output to one decimal point, how many of the outputs match the target, so actually the ratio of the outputs which were within 95% accuracy. On the bottom one the average error can be seen per target, the average error including all the targets were about 0.15. Apart from these the left picture is showing the loss for each batch in the same manner as in the previous training with direction.

3.1.4.2 Training with the inclusion of phase information

After the sigmoid function with single pictures was inspected, I modified the network for being able to accept the phase informations as well. Instead of having one input channel at the first layer, I modified it for two and also the training method was modified for being able to accept a 2 channel input. The pictures in this training round were the same as in the previous one, the only difference was that the input contained the phase data as well. Using this configuration I got the following test results after the training:

Figure 13: *The test results using sigmoid activation function and phase informations as well.*

As it can be seen on *Figure 13*, the ratio of the well assessed test samples increased, especially at the two boundaries (at 0.0-0.1 and 0.9-1.0). This means that those pictures, that belong to a boundary target have more similarities compared to each other and also better detectable features. In parallel, the average error decreased, here the biggest difference can be spotted at the boundaries again, but they are quite similar all over the targets.

Apart from the depiction of the accuracy in numbers, another good practice for showing the precision is to present that how the picture would look like if we would shift the actual distance with the magnitude, which was estimated by the network. In the following pictures we can see such examples:

Figure 14: *Examples, which show how the pictures would look like if we would propagate the holograms with the predicted distance of the network.*

Here, the left pictures are raw unfocused pictures from the test set, the middle ones are those which we would get if we would shift the actual focus distance by the number that was estimated by the network, and the right ones are the pictures in the focus. As it can be seen on the pictures, the focus is quite accurate, the average L1 loss with this method was about 0.09-0.08 which means approximately 91-92% accuracy.

3.2 Image segmentation and object classification

As it was mentioned previously, my thesis work is composed of two main topics. The first part was the estimation of the focus distance and the second one is the segmentation and the classification of the objects, which are present on the images. During my work this part had a higher share in terms of the development time and I also used a bit different kind of development approaches compared to the focus distance estimation.

In terms of the data — which were used for the training and the validation purposes — here another database was used, where the images were exported for these specific segmentation and classification tasks. In this database both the magnitude and the phase images were available, however I faced with the issue, that the number of labelled images, which later could be used as the ground truth during the training and the validation was limited and often not accurate enough. This labelling process can be very time consuming if it has to be done manually, so to overcome this main issue and also handle those ones, which may come up later during the development, I developed an image processing tool, which can be considered as a "manager" of the input database.

3.2.1 The image processing tool

When I started to work on the image segmentation and object classification part of my thesis work, the first step was to develop an image processing tool for handling those issues, which may come up related to the input database. Just like the neural networks in my work, the tool was developed in the python programming language and for the image processing purposes the OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision) library was used. As its longer name states, this library is a very famous and widely used framework for image processing and computer vision related problems with various different functions for handling these issues.

During my work, the first and main issue related to the input database was the one, which was mentioned above, namely that the number of labelled images in the database was limited and often in the labelled cases it was not accurate enough. Since the labelling process is very expensive in terms of time, the automation of labelled image generation was the first functionality which was implemented into this tool.

Then, as the next step it was also important to augment the already labelled images to have even more training and validation/test samples. For that I implemented a function, which took all parts of a given recording (the magnitude, the phase and the previously generated labelled image) and based on random parameters transformed the images using

translations and rotations. This procedure was also important for the proper learning of the later implemented segmentation networks, since it transformed the objects to other parts of the images (in the original recordings the objects are located almost exclusively in the middle section of the images), so after that the locations of the objects were uniformly distributed among the different samples.

Apart from these two main functionalities, there were some additional minor features of the tool, which helped managing the input database. These were among others moving images from one place to another after a labelling or an augmentation process has been applied, make minor image renaming (usually an exchange of a few letters) for being able to group the images of a given recording much more easily, or removing such recordings with all of their images, where no objects are present.

In the following sections the two main functionalities, the label generation and the data augmentation will be described in more details.

3.2.1.1 Generating labelled images

Label generation for image segmentation purposes means, that we take the input images (these may be the magnitude or the phase image or both) and based on them mark those pixels with a specific color, which belong to the objects. The number of different colors which are used is depending on the segmentation type. In case of a single segmentation — where we are only interested in the presence and absence of an object for a given pixel — two colors are enough (a color for the objects and a color for the background, which is usually black). However for more complex segmentation tasks like in the case of the semantic segmentation, the objects which belong to different types are marked with different colors, so the number of colors in this case is determined by the number of object types in the training plus one color for the background. An even more difficult segmentation task is, when we want to distinguish the different object instances, so in this case the object type does not matter for a given pixel, only the object instance it belongs to. The name of this type of segmentation is the previously mentioned instance segmentation. In this situation the used number of colors is determined by the number of object instances in the image and like in the previous case we have to add plus one color for the background. This is a much more difficult task not just in terms of the implementation and training of the network, but also in the case of the automated label generation. During my work, the first two segmentation types were used, so the label

generation was aligned to the single and semantic segmentation problem types.

For generating labelled images I tried out different methods. My first idea was to look for built-in OpenCV functions, which were developed for edge detection. Using these functions, the first step would be to detect the boundaries of the objects, which are present on our DHM images. Then, in my plan the subsequent step was to filter out the false positive edges. These are those pixels, which are predicted by the edge detectors as edges, but in the reality they are not. These false positive edges can be distinguished from the true positive ones based on a major property. In case of the real object edges, when we do an edge traversal the starting point should be the same as the end point as they are enclosing the object, however in the false positive edges, this is not the case as they do not enclose anything and have a random-like form. Then, as the next step starting from the remaining true positive boundaries with the usage of recursive algorithms fill the inside of the objects with the specified color. Here the starting direction of the recursive filling algorithm (RFA) would be determined by the relation of the selected starting point coordinates and the coordinates of the other points, which participate in the enclosing of the given object. For example, if we pick randomly a starting point from the top section of the boundary and calculate the average y coordinates of the other boundary points enclosing the given object, then we will get the result that the average y coordinate value of the other points is lower than the y coordinate of the starting point. If we compare both the x and y coordinates in this manner, then the randomly picked starting point can be precisely localised within the boundary, which determines the starting direction of the RFA.

This method requires very accurate edge detection for the real edges, since the filtering logic would filter out real edges as well in case of the presence of a single gap in the object boundaries. In other words if there is a single pixel, which should be marked by the OpenCV functions as an "edge" but it is not marked (false negative outcome of the edge detection), then the RFA will not be able to fill the real objects with the specified color as the real object boundaries will be also filtered out and thus it would not have an edge pixel, where the filling can start.

As the edge detection functions, I tried out two different techniques, these were the Sobel and the Canny edge detectors. Comparing the two methods, the Sobel technique has the advantage, that it is more simple and thus it has a better time efficiency, however it produces rougher edges. In contrast to that, the Canny algorithm uses addi-

tionally a so-called Non-maxima suppression and thresholding technique, which results in a smoother edge detection, but it has less time efficiency.

During the implementation of the label generator function, which uses these two edge detector techniques, the first task was to fine tune the parameters of these edge detectors. For that I used different loops with various increment numbers to try out different parameter values. However, apart from a few exceptions, for most of the DHM images the detection was not accurate enough (there were gaps in the boundaries of the objects) and thus in most cases the filling algorithm could not perform well. As it turned out, this is due to the fact that in the DHM recordings in most cases the boundaries of the objects are not sharp enough, so apart from a very few exceptions (images with sharp object edges) this edge detection technique was not working. Because of that I had to figure out another technique for automating this labelling process.

This new method was simpler and faster than my first idea with the edge detection since it did not require recursions on the images. Instead, it uses the famous masking technique, which is a commonly used method in python, especially on numpy arrays (OpenCV handles the images in form of numpy arrays). Masking can be described shortly as selecting given array locations (in case of 2D images this is a pixel) based on some boolean conditions. And since in numpy the underlying implementation is done in the C programming language, this process can be performed really fast.

In case of our DHM images, we have an important property, which can be the source for the masking condition. In most of our recordings the objects are darker than the surroundings, so the idea would be, that if I can find a proper threshold value for that, then those pixels could be selected, where the values are less than this threshold (Since the DHM recordings are grayscale and not RGB images, we only have to care about the brightness of the specific pixels). Of course there are some object types — these are the so-called phase objects — where this method cannot work. We could see already such images on *Figure 14*, where the pictures of the second and the third row contain phase objects. In these cases unfortunately this method does not work, since the inside of the objects are not darker and not even brighter than the background, so in these cases only an edge detection method could work for the automation. In our database I labelled a bunch of these images manually by hand, and then their number were raised by the data augmentation method of this image processing tool (see later).

So apart from these phase object containing images, this masking method worked quite

well, of course this processing technique also required some image processing steps before the masking could take place. The first step was actually to normalize the values of the pixels into the range of [0 1] and then based on the mode of the function do a kind of mixing of the magnitude and phase images. The normalization was a quite simple step, dividing all pixels with the maximum value on the image. Then, I applied the mixing of the images based on the mode, this could be 2 different types. In the first case only the magnitude image was used for the label generation in its original form, so in this case there was no mixing between the images. In the other case, the magnitude and phase image for a given recording was mixed with a weighting factor of 0.5 for both images and this resulted the image, which was then further processed in the subsequent steps. I also made experiments with "phase image only mode", where the magnitude image was not used at all, however this method did not give good results, the magnitude image presence in the label generation was crucial.

After these first two steps have been applied, the next task was to apply a filter on the resulted image to reduce the possibility of noise related artefacts. For that, I used the gaussian blurring method of the OpenCV library to act as a low-pass filter and smooth the input images (The previously mentioned edge detectors, the Sobel and the Canny also uses gaussian blurring as a noise reduction technique). Here I also had to fine tune the parameters. After conducting several experiments on them, it turned out that the best kernel size for the blurring was 7x7 and a standard deviation of 1.7 - 2.

Following the gaussian blurring, the last steps were to determine the masking condition based on the mixed and filtered image and then apply the masking using this condition. Since the different images have different base brightness, this threshold condition could not be hard coded as a fixed value, it had to be calculated for each image one-by-one. For calculating this criteria I firstly took the minimum pixel value of the image (the darkest point) assuming that it belongs to an object (since the objects are mostly darker than the surroundings except the phase objects). Then, the mean brightness was also calculated and using these two values I applied the following formula:

$$cond = min + (mean - min) \cdot param \quad (1)$$

Here *cond* represents the condition, *min* is the darkest point on the image, *mean* is the previously calculated mean or average brightness value of the image and *param* is a parameter, which was usually varying between 0.5 and 0.7. After this condition has been calculated, those pixels were selected with the masking technique, where the value was

less than this condition.

This kind of label generation was also not perfect, during a run with a given *param* parameter value a group of images were correctly labelled and an other group of them were not. In those images, which were not correctly labelled with a given *param* value, mainly the inside of the objects were not coloured out fully, the boundaries were properly detected as it can be seen on the following figure:

Figure 15: *The magnitude image and the generated labelled image in case of an inaccurate labelling. As it can be seen, the boundaries of the object are properly detected and the inaccuracy occurs in the inside.*

Because of this issue I had to do the label generation iteratively. This means, that firstly I set the *param* and the mode of the generation to a given value, ran the generation and then I had to select those images, which were correctly labelled and delete the incorrectly labelled ones. Then, again I set the *param* to a different value and did the steps of the previous iteration. Although this label generation became at the end semi-automatic due to these inaccuracies, it was also a huge help and spared lot of time. Also, in the inaccurately labelled images, these errors were mostly minor and could be corrected very easily and fast with some basic tools, for instance with paint.

3.2.1.2 Data augmentation

As mentioned previously, apart from the labelled image generation, the other main functionality of the tool was to augment the number of images using transformations. This is a very efficient way to increase the training and test/validation set size based on already labelled images, because at once the same transformation is applied to all the components (magnitude, phase and labelled image) of a given recording and thus the newly created images will not need new labelling procedure.

Transformation means, that — based on different transformation parameters — each pixel of the given image are moved into other pixel positions and thus the position and the orientation of the objects will be changed as well. Including these transformed images into the training and validation sets lets the network encounter even more objects also in different locations on the images (the objects will be uniformly distributed among the image sections), which helps to learn more general features and avoid overfitting.

The transformation in my function is composed of two main parts: rotation and translation. During the rotation part, firstly a random number is generated between 0 and 360 to serve as the degree of rotation. The axis of the rotation is the middle point of the image, so actually width/2 and height/2. Since the objects on our original images are almost exclusively located in the middle section, this point is usually inside the objects. Thus, the middle point of them is really close to the axis point, so they also can be considered as the axis of the rotation.

These two parameters — the degree of rotation and the axis point — are then passed to the OpenCV function (*getRotationMatrix2D*), which creates a transformation matrix for the rotation. Generating a transformation matrix for the rotation is simple using the base rotation matrix

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where θ is the angle of rotation. However in our case, because the axis of rotation is not the origin, a third "translational" column also has to be added with specific formulas and apart from that the $\sin(\theta)$ components in the first two columns have to swap signs compared to the base rotation matrix:

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) & (1 - \cos(\theta)) \cdot axis.x - \sin(\theta) \cdot axis.y \\ -\sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) & (1 - \cos(\theta)) \cdot axis.y + \sin(\theta) \cdot axis.x \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Here *axis.x* and *axis.y* are the x and y coordinates of the rotation axis, respectively. This is the formula of the previously mentioned function, which is used for calculating the rotation matrix. During the transformation, an additional third coordinate is added to the given pixel point with a hard coded value of 1, and thus the third column of the transformation matrix acts as a single translation vector.

Following this step and using the generated matrix, the transformation was applied with a specific function for this purpose (*warpAffine*).

After the rotation has been applied, the following step was to do the same for the translation. The translation consists of two parts, it has a horizontal(x) and a vertical(y) component. For these two components, again a random number is generated, between the ranges $[-width/2, width/2]$ and $[-height/2, height/2]$ for the x and y components, respectively. These limits were important, because — just like in case of the rotation — again the middle point ($width/2, height/2$) of the image is considered as the starting point, and using these limit values the objects can end up in any location without shifting them completely out from the images. Using these parameters I created the translation matrix (I did not use here the OpenCV library due to the simplicity of the matrix), which can be seen on the following equation:

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & t_x \\ 0 & 1 & t_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Here the third column, the t_x and t_y are responsible for performing the translation for the x and y coordinates, respectively. As the last step, this matrix was also given to the *warpAffine* function to perform the transformation.

After the transformations, those pixels on the new images, from where the original pixels were shifted out completely are replaced by default with black color. This is a good replacement for the labelled images — where only the object containing pixels have a different color from black — however for the magnitude and phase images this could cause problems, because it acts as a background color. For these two image types, the average brightness of the original image is calculated and the "outshifted" portions are replaced with these colors, so in this way they have a background-like color intensity.

On the following figure an example can be seen about the original images and their transformed variations:

Figure 16: *The original image components and their transformed variations. From left to right the magnitude, the phase and the labelled(GT) images can be seen. In this example the rotation was applied by 213° , the x translation was 38 pixels in the negative direction (towards left) and the y translation was 21 pixels in the positive direction (downwards). On the magnitude and phase images, the outshifted image portions were replaced by the average color intensity of the original images.*

3.2.2 The object segmentor and classifier networks

After the image processing tool was developed and I had a high number of labelled and transformed images, I could continue my work with the implementation of the image segmentor and object classifier networks. As I mentioned previously, at the start of this development I used different kind of approaches compared to the focus distance estimator networks. As it is visible on *Table 1*, at the start of the development of the focus distance estimator net I used immediately a relatively complex network with five convolutional layers and the numbers of the output feature maps(OFM) following the convolutional layers were also relatively high (at the output of the fourth layer it was already 256). Apart from that, the training and the validation steps were strictly separated, which means that the testing/validation step was executed after a training was ended.

In contrast to these, for the object segmentor and classifier networks I started with simpler architectures and during the trainings after each epoch a test has been executed on the given validation sets to monitor the actual state of the networks. This latter step helps to avoid overfitting for a given training set and in the same time allows to adjust the training time to the performance achieved on the validation/test set.

During the development my first target was to implement a network, which is capable to segment and detect the objects, which are present on the images, but at this step the type of the objects did not matter. So here the aim was to develop a simple segmentation network.

3.2.2.1 Simple object segmentor net (SOSN)

As always, the first step in the development of the simple segmentation network was to design a basic architecture, which serves my purposes, so it should be this time as simple as possible and still able to perform the basic object segmentation tasks. For this purpose I designed and implemented a net with three blocks, from which the first two blocks contains two basic layers: A convolutional layer with a kernel size of 5x5, a stride of 1 and a padding value of 2, and an average pooling layer with the same stride and padding parameters. With this parameter configuration my aim was to try out an architecture, which does not reduce the width and height dimensions during the convolutional and pooling operations and thus at the end no deconvolutions will be needed to restore

the original image dimensions. Due to that, the complexity of the network is much smaller than the complexity of the conventional segmentation networks and because of that it requires much less hardware resources. The disadvantage of this configuration and architecture is that it reduces the capability of the network to see image context related informations, it has a smaller field of view. For enhancing the image context view of the convolutional kernels, the kernel size has a bigger 5x5 value compared to the original U-Net's kernel size of 3x3[25], and this is the case for the average pooling layers as well.

Regarding the number of the OFMs, here I also tried to start with low numbers. This means, that in the first block the number of the OFMs of the convolutional layer was set first to 16, which is again much less than the 64 OFMs of the U-Net's first block. Since the input of the whole network consists of two grayscale images (magnitude and phase) for a given recording, the number of the input channels in the first convolutional layer was set always to 2 (Unlike in case of the focus net, here the phase images were available already from the beginning of the development). For the second block's convolutional layer the number of input feature maps was of course 16 and its output was set to 32.

The third block of the network was designed to serve as the output of the net. At the very beginning it contained only a convolutional layer with 32 input feature maps coming from the second block and a single OFM, which contains already the segmented output of the net. Here the previously mentioned kernel and padding parameters have also been changed, instead of having a kernel size of 5x5, it has a size of 1x1. This size change is due to the fact that here the context related information of the specific pixels are not needed anymore, the output for them is only depending on the weighted sum of the previously generated 32 OFMs on that specific pixel location. To preserve the width and height dimensions of the single OFM of this third convolutional layer, the padding parameter also had to be adapted to the new size of the kernel, and thus it was set to 0. For the activation function — just like in the case of the latter version of the focus distance estimator net — the sigmoid function was used, to map the output of the net in the range of $[0, 1]$. This output can be thought of as a value for each pixel, which describes the probability regarding the presence of an object on the specific pixel. For determining the loss compared to the target values, mean squared error was implemented and for achieving better performance Adam optimizer was used with a learning rate of 0.001. During the trainings I tried out different batch sizes, this varied between 5-40. For that it turned out that the best performance can be achieved with 10 recordings for

a batch, even though an epoch contained approximately 15000 recordings.

For the training and validation/test sets I had here approximately 500 labelled base recordings, which were divided between the two sets, each having through that ~ 250 of them. After that these base recordings were augmented separately up to 15000 recordings by the transformations, so overall I had ~ 15000 recordings for the training and for the validation sets as well. These pictures contained a variety of object types, also phase objects — where the base color of the object does not really differ from the background color of the image — were present among them. Here as I mentioned previously only the presence of them did count, the type did not, so it did not matter either which color was used on the labelled/ground truth images for marking them, as here the target tensor (which is used as the reference for calculating the loss) generation during the reading of the images was based on a simple logic: Is the color of the given pixel on the GT image black or not? If it is black, the target value for that given pixel is 0, and if it is anything else, then it's 1. Apart from the target tensor generation during the reading of the recordings, the resolution of the images was reduced from 128x128 to 64x64 to enhance the learning speed of the net.

So, as the first round I tried out this architecture, with the previously described input recordings. At first, during the trainings I faced the main issue, that the loss did not decrease with the same manner. Sometimes it was decreasing till a point where it was stuck, and in some other cases it decreased gradually till a point where it was already acceptable ($\sim 0.02-0.04$). Because of that, in some tries I had to restart the whole training a few times until it did not stuck at a certain loss values and could go further. To solve this issue, I tried to modify the learning rate parameter of the Adam optimizer, but it did not help. Since it was completely random when did the loss stuck at a certain value and when did it reach an acceptable performance, my idea was that these cases are depending on the initialization values of the weights of the net (the values of the convolutional kernels) and also on the randomness of the input. During the training, at the beginning of each epoch the input recordings were shuffled up in the containing array and then they were chosen for the batches in the order of their new locations. Thus, the recording contents of the batches were completely random, which may cause big differences in the value distribution among them.

For these kind of problems there is a commonly used technique, which is also used in

the article of *Valadares et al*[30] and this is the so-called batch normalization method. During this procedure, the means and the variances for the given batch is calculated per dimension and using that the inputs of the layers can be normalized through re-centering and re-scaling. Because of these properties, as the next solution idea, I implemented batch normalization layers after each convolutional layer, and then the output of these layers were given to the ReLU activation functions as it is visible in the table below:

Layer	Layer type	In channels	Out channels	Kernel size	Stride	Padding
1	Conv.	2	16	5	1	2
2	BatchN. + ReLu	16	16	-	-	-
3	AvgPool	16	16	5	1	2
4	Conv.	16	32	5	1	2
5	BatchN. + ReLu	32	32	-	-	-
6	AvgPool	32	32	5	1	2
7	Conv.	32	1	1	1	0
8	BatchN. + Sigmoid	1	1	-	-	-

Table 2: *The architecture of the SOSN after the batch normalization layers have also been included. Here the layers 1-3 belong to the first block, layers 4-6 represent the second block, and the last two layers belong to the third one.*

After these BatchNorm layers have been applied, they resolved immediately the issue regarding the stucked loss values. This means that from that point the loss values decreased gradually with the same manner in each training run and could reach even better loss values than previously during the successful runs. On the following figure, the output of the newly created architecture can be seen. The left image illustrates the learning curve of the net and the right images show an example about the segmented output on the validation/test set:

Figure 17: The learning curve of the net and an example output after a ~ 30 minute training. On the left image the blue line represent the loss values on the training set and the orange line represent it on the validation set in each epoch. On the right side on the top, the magnitude and phase images can be seen for a given recording from the test set and under them the segmented output of the net with blue color. Next to it the ground truth image can be seen with green color for a comparison.

As it can be seen, the network could reach good performance (target loss was under 0.01 on the test set) and for that approximately only half an hour was needed. Due to the success of this architecture I continued my work with it for my next target, to implement a semantic segmentor network.

3.2.2.2 Simple semantic segmentor net (SSSN)

Due to the success of the previously described architecture with the BatchNorm layers, I continued my work with the adaptation of it for the semantic segmentation tasks. Here again my first task was to prepare the input database. The previously used database for the simple segmentor net was not good in this case, because here the recordings were not separated based on the object types, and also the name of the recordings did not contain this information either. So I started with a new database, where the recordings were sorted based on this criteria. Firstly, I selected two main algae groups, the *Klebsormidium* (fon), and the *Scenedesmus* (sco), which were extended later with the *tricornutum* (trc).

Here I labelled approximately 100 base recordings for a group, which were divided for the training and the validation sets, so there were ~ 50 of them from each group in the test and training sets as well. These were then augmented separately by a factor of 100, which means that I had ~ 5000 recording per group per set, so overall there were

again approximately 15000 recordings in a set. It was important in this case to have nearly the same amount of the different types to avoid the overfitting of the net for the more abundant types.

For the adaptation three main properties of the net came into consideration. The compulsory change among them was to adapt the number of the OFMs of the last layer to be equal with the number of the object types, which will be presented to the network. This change was necessary, because in this case the different object types are independent, each of them are having a kernel in the last layer, which scans the previously generated feature maps for the specific object type. Thus, if the network performs well these feature maps should be nearly disjunct, which means that for a specific pixel only one map of them should give high output value, the other ones should be low. This fact is also affecting of course the target tensor generation during the reading of the images. For that I modified this part of the code to read an input config (json) file, which contains all the relevant information regarding the different types. These are two properties: the RGB color of the given type on the GT images and the index of the OFM in the last layer, which represents the net's estimation for the given type. Using these properties, and the already mentioned masking technique, the RGB channels of the GT images can be separately compared with the RGB color value of the given type, and if all three color channels match for a given pixel, then the presence of the object type can be marked on the target tensor by setting 1 for the given pixel at the acquired feature map index (and leaving a 0 value for the other feature maps on the given pixel coordinate).

Besides that, I also tried to find a more suitable activation function for the last layer. This change was not compulsory, since the previously used sigmoid function could also be used for this purpose, however in this case it's a good approach to use such a function, which considers all the independently generated OFMs and then scales them appropriately. Because if we say, that these values are probabilities, then the sum of the feature maps for a given pixel should add up to 1.

To map the output values of a given pixel in this range, a commonly used function is the so-called softmax, which has the following formula for the calculation:

$$s(x_i) = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum_{k=1}^n e^{x_k}} \quad (5)$$

Here x_i represents the output for the given pixel on the i-th feature map, and n is the

total number of OFMs. Using this activation function, the previously described target tensor generation and the number of OFMs had to be modified a little bit. For making it work, an additional layer had to be added to both of them to represent the background pixels as a separate type, since otherwise in these pixels the softmax would give false outputs for the other object types due to the upscaling of their values (if we would use sigmoid, it would not be necessarily needed, because it does not re-scale the single outputs to add up to 1). During the evaluation and the generation of the estimated output images, the maximum probability value among the different types are selected and marked on the image with the color of the given type. So we say, that a given pixel is estimated by the net to belong to a given type, if the feature map of the given type has the highest output value compared to the others.

And last but not least, the third adaptation was that I increased a little bit the number of the output channels from the first and middle layers as well to have more kernels, which can be adapted to specific features on the images. Here the magnitude of the increase was a factor of 1.5 compared to the previous values. On the following table the adapted architecture is visible including the previously mentioned 3 main changes (with 3 object types):

Layer	Layer type	In channels	Out channels	Kernel size	Stride	Padding
1	Conv.	2	24	5	1	2
2	BatchN. + ReLu	24	24	-	-	-
3	AvgPool	24	24	5	1	2
4	Conv.	24	48	5	1	2
5	BatchN. + ReLu	48	48	-	-	-
6	AvgPool	48	48	5	1	2
7	Conv.	48	3+1(Bg)	1	1	0
8	BatchN. + Softmax	4	4	-	-	-

Table 3: *The architecture of the SSSN after the adaptation has been done. As it can be seen the number of output maps in the middle and first layers was increased by a factor of 1.5 and in the last layers both the number of output features and the activation function was changed.*

After this architecture has been adapted, I started a few preliminary runs with two (fon, sco), and then with three object types (fon, sco, trc). Since I got promising results, I modified the net to consider rather the elapsed time than the loss threshold value as the stop signal for the learning, and then I started a longer, 8 hour long run to have a more representative result about the capability of the net. For that I got reliable results with rarely occurring errors, however for being able to better evaluate these results, as

the next step I implemented two versions of the "state-of-the-art" U-Net architectures.

3.2.2.3 Comparing the net with the U-Net architecture

As mentioned in the previous section, for being able to better evaluate the results of the SSSN, I continued my work with the implementation of two U-Net architectures, that still can be considered as one of the best architecture invented so far. These two nets were two modified versions of the original U-Net, which were adapted to our input recordings and also to the properties, of the SSSN. The difference between the two versions was, that in the first version (complete U-Net, CUN) all the 4 basic contracting and expanding blocks were present with the same number of OFMs, while in my second version (simplified U-Net, SUN) the last contracting and the first expanding blocks (with the highest number of OFMs), with skipped connection were removed, for having a more simplified version of it.

These adaptations mean, that firstly for being able to accept the magnitude and the phase images, the input channel of the first convolutional layer in the first block was modified to have 2 input channels. Apart from that since our images have a resolution of 64x64 pixels for a faster learning, it could not be allowed to reduce the dimensions during the convolutions, because simply due to the contracting pathway the resolution would not be enough at the end of the 4th contracting block. Because of that I increased the padding parameter of all the convolutional layers to 1, which enables with the original kernel size of 3x3 to preserve the dimensions during the convolutions. This increase in the padding parameter was set in the deconvolutional layers as well.

Compared to the original version, the generation of the skipped connections also had to be modified. Originally a cropping was needed, since due to the unpadded property there were losses at the border pixels after each convolutions [25]. However in my case, since my versions preserve the dimensions during the convolutions, and the border pixels are also highly covered by the kernels at the padded sides, this cropping change was not necessary and also could not be afforded either due to the low image resolutions. This implies, that a further difference between the original and my versions was that in the original U-Net due to the cropping there were dimension differences between the contracting and the corresponding expanding pathways, however in my case the dimensions in the corresponding pathways were totally equal.

Considering the further properties of my U-Net versions, here I also tried to minimize the difference compared to the SSSN. I did that, because I wanted to focus on the error of the SSSN, which was caused by the difference between the number of OFMs, the absence of the contracting and expanding pathways, and also the lack of the skipped connections. Due to that I introduced batch norm layers after each convolutional layer, and the activation function in the last layer was set to be the softmax. Instead of using the cross entropy loss function like in the original paper [25], I used here again the mean squared error loss and apart from that, like previously, I also used Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001.

Regarding the input database, the same training and validation recordings were used as in the SSSN, for having a good base for the comparison. Considering the batch size of the input, here in the original U-Net only a single image was used, in my versions however I stucked to the size which was used in the SSSN, so it was set to 10.

After all these parameters have been set and both of my U-Net versions were ready, I started again 8 hour long trainings for both versions. On the following figure the outputs of the 3 networks (including the SSSN) are visible on the validation set after the 8 hour long trainings and the learning curves can also be seen:

Figure 18: *The outputs of my implemented networks and their learning curves during the 8 hour trainings. On the top section 3 input recordings are visible, 1 from each group. The type fon is marked by red, sco is marked by green and the trc type is marked by blue color. I selected intentionally such recordings, where the SSSN had some errors (rare cases, just to see the difference). Column a) marks the GT image, and b), c), d) belongs to the SSSN, CUN, and SUN version, respectively. On the section below, the learning curves of my networks are visible, marked with the same letters.*

3.2.2.4 Conclusion

As it can be seen on *Figure 18*, the errors, which were present in the SSSN images disappeared in the U-Net versions and it's also visible that the SUN's and CUN's performance was quite similar. The SSSN performance was a bit worse, an error of ~ 0.003 could be reached on the test set compared to the ~ 0.002 MSE of the U-Net versions. The following table summarizes these differences on the classified pixel level as well:

	SSSN	CUN	SUN
Fon	92.68%	95.34%	95.78%
Sco	75.51%	86.44%	91.03%
Trc	80.95%	85.05%	85.62%
Background	99.75%	99.81%	99.78%

Table 4: *The ratio of the correctly classified pixels in each group for the whole test set. As it can be seen the SUN's performance is the best in each group except the background. This is probably due to the fact, that the SUN has a simpler architecture compared to CUN, and during the 8 hour long trainings more epochs and backpropagations could be performed. Regarding the SSSN, apart from the Sco type, the differences were not too big.*

On *Table 4* it can be seen that the SSSN performance was worse also in the pixel classification levels, however apart from the Sco these differences were not too big. Also, in case of the Sco, the errors were focused on a few recordings and their transformed variations (the distribution of the error among the recordings were not uniform at all), where the classification was completely wrong, which then decreased significantly its overall accuracy for this type.

So in general it can be concluded, that a few contracting and expanding layers were missing from the SSSN (image context view), but since the simpler SUN could slightly outperform the more complex CUN, probably even less layers (1-2 convolutional layers with dimension halving pooling layers + 1-2 deconvolutional layers) and OFMs (starting from 24 and ending at 48-96) would be also enough to reach very similar performance as the U-Nets in these kinds of images. The advantage of the SSSN was, that it required much less hardware resources (6GB of RAM vs more than 32 GB of RAM in case of the U-Nets), and the transformation of its layers to become contracting and expanding could probably lead to very similar performance. For the simple segmentation tasks, where no object classification is needed, the SOSN reached quite good performance, so for this kind of problem and images it's not needed to introduce contracting and expanding layers.

4 Summary

During my thesis work I had two main tasks. The first one was to implement a deep learning based model, which is capable to learn the proper estimation of the focus distance of our DHM recordings. For this problem the most suitable technique was to implement a convolutional neural network.

Thus, I implemented a neural network with 6 layers and then tried out 3 main architectural setup for reaching the best performance. In the first one, I used hyperbolic tangent activation function in the last layer with single images, but here I faced with the issue, that although the network was capable to determine the absolute distance quite well, often it could not distinguish the positive and negative distances (the signs were often swapped). In this case only magnitude images were used, phase information was not included in the input.

The second setup was using sigmoid activation function in the last layer, also with single channel input images. Here I only considered the absolute value of the distances and that was given to the network as the target. The performance here was already much better the average L1 loss was around 0.15, so 85% accuracy was reached in average.

And the last training type for the focus distance estimator net was using sigmoid activation function with 2 channel input data, where apart from the magnitude image data, the network also got phase informations as the second channel input. The best performance was achieved using this method, the average L1 loss was reduced to 0.08-0.09, so in average 91-92% accuracy was reached.

Then, my second task was to implement again deep learning based models, which are capable to segment the objects on our DHM recordings and also classify them based on their types. Here an additional task was that I had to generate the GT images as well, because the available ones were not accurate enough for proper training and validation. Therefore, I developed an image processing tool, which although at the end was not completely automatic (it required manual checking and in some cases also error correction), but it spared lots of my time and for most of the image types it could be used quite reliably. Besides the labelling, it was further developed to be able to augment the available base recordings through transformations, which made it possible for the nets to also encounter with even more object orientations in different positions (not just in the center).

Then, after I had a high number of input recordings I implemented a SOSN, where only the segmentation of the objects were relevant, the type of them did not matter. Here my idea was to implement such a convolutional net, which does not reduce the dimensions of the images to avoid the necessity of the expanding pathway of the conventional segmentation networks. Firstly, I implemented a really simple network with 3 basic blocks, low number of OFMs and sigmoid activation function in the last layer. Here I faced with the issue that during the trainings in many cases the error was not decreasing gradually, often it was stucked at certain values. For solving this problem I introduced batch norm layers in each block after the convolutional layers, which at the end resulted in fast learning(25 minutes were enough for reaching good results) and also reliable performance.

As the next step of my work, I tried to adapt the SOSN architecture to semantic segmentation tasks. 3 main changes have been made for that:

1. The number of output feature maps in the last layer had to be increased to be equal with the number of object types (+1 for the background in case of softmax)
2. Sigmoid was replaced to softmax, which is much more suitable for these kind of tasks.
3. Increasing all the OFMs by a factor of 1.5.

With this modified net I run more representative, 8 hour long trainings, where at the end an error of ~ 0.003 could be reached, which visually means some error artefacts on a few recordings and on their transformed variations. For being able to evaluate these results better, as the following step I implemented 2 U-Net versions adapted to our input recordings and also to the properties of the SSSN. The difference between the 2 nets was, that in the first version all the blocks of the original U-Net was present, while in the second one the last contracting and first expanding block was removed. With these nets after an 8 hour long run an error of ~ 0.002 could be reached, which visually was enough to correct most of those error artefacts, which were present on the output of the SSSN.

5 Further development areas

Of course there are still areas, where the performance of my networks could be improved. Currently I have the following improvement ideas:

1. For the focus distance estimator net:
 - (a) Optimizing the architecture to have a faster learning speed. This includes mainly the reduction of the number of layers and also the OFMs in the convolutional layers.
 - (b) Using the image processing tool to augment and create more variations of these focus distance inputs as well.
 - (c) Introducing in-training evaluation of the test set, like in the case of the segmentation networks.
 - (d) Trying out new training methods like adding phase information to the training with directions or having experiments with such recordings which have only positive or negative distances.
2. For the segmentation networks:
 - (a) Introducing even more object types into the training and validation.
 - (b) Transforming the layers of the SSSN to have ~ 2 contracting and expanding blocks, because based on the experiences with the SSSN, CUN and SUN, a much simpler architecture with bigger image context view could be the optimal solution (considering hardware resources and performance) for these kind of recordings and task.
 - (c) Introducing the intersection over union (IoU) loss evaluation technique, which may suit better for segmentation and object detection problems.
3. Connecting the segmentation networks to the output of the focus distance estimator net to segment the estimated in-focus images.

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